

Synthesis of *N*-Methylindolo[2,3-*c*]pyrans and related Compounds

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Acylation of 2-carboxy-*N*-methylindole-3-acetic acid or the related ester have led to indolo[2,3-*c*]pyrans convertible to norharman derivatives.

AS an extension of our studies on the synthesis of benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyrans¹ we report herein our studies on the acylation of 2-carboxy-*N*-methylindole-3-acetic acid² (1) in view of the recent publication of Bailey *et al.*³ in this area.

Pyridine catalysed acylation of 1 or the related anhydride⁴ (6) gave mixture of the acid [8; ν_{\max} 1 725, 1 695 and 1 680 cm^{-1}], the acetylpyran [9; ν_{\max} 1 725 and 1 680 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.35 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.64 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.16 (3H, s, NCH_3) and 7.0–7.73 (4H, m, ArH)] together with a high melting compound (m.p. 292°) having the composition $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (ν_{\max} 1 725, 1 705, 1 880 cm^{-1}) possibly 7, in analogy with the reported work in literature^{4,5} wherein detailed mechanism for the formation of compounds analogous to 7 and 9 in a similar reaction has been suggested. It has been shown⁴ that acylation precedes decarboxylation and indeed can occur without decarboxylation. The formation of diacylation product has been rationalised in terms of the enhanced reactivity arising from the carboxyl group at 2-position. Acylation at the room temperature however furnished one compound which may be formulated as 10 [ν_{\max} 1 770 and 1 730 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.07 (3H, s, $\text{O}-\text{COCH}_3$), 2.57 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.07 (3H, s, NCH_3), 7.07–7.5 (3H, m, ArH) and 7.95 (1H, d, *J* 8Hz, *peri*-H)]. This on alkaline hydrolysis gave the acid (3; ν_{\max} 1 700 and 1 670 cm^{-1}) which readily cyclised to 11 (ν_{\max} 1 725 cm^{-1}). The compound was also obtained by the decarboxylation of 8.

The ester (2) on formylation with methyl formate⁷ gave 4 (ν_{\max} 2 925, 1 705, 1 685 and 1 660 cm^{-1}) which on warming with acid underwent cyclisation to give 12 (ν_{\max} 1 730 and 1 715 cm^{-1}). Hydrolysis of 12 with acids gave the acid (13; ν_{\max} 1 720 and 1 705 cm^{-1}) which on decarboxylation gave 14 (ν_{\max} 1 715 cm^{-1}). Similarly, acylation of 2 with ethyl oxalate gave 5 (ν_{\max} 1 740, 1 685 and 1 665 cm^{-1}) which was similarly cyclised to the di-ester (15; ν_{\max} 1 740 and 1 730 cm^{-1}).

The pyran (11) and 14 on treatment with ammonia at elevated temperature gave respectively

16 (ν_{\max} 1 645 cm^{-1}) and 17 (ν_{\max} 1 645 cm^{-1}). It may be mentioned that 17 has been prepared earlier by different routes⁸ and converted into norharman.

- 1; $\text{R}_1 = \text{COOH}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$
 2; $\text{R}_1 = \text{COOMe}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{COOMe}$
 3; $\text{R}_1 = \text{COOH}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$
 4; $\text{R}_1 = \text{COOMe}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{CHCOOMe}$

6

7

- 8; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{COOH}$
 9; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{COCH}_3$
 10; $\text{R}_1 = \text{OCOMe}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{OOMe}$
 11; $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$
 12; $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{COOMe}$
 13; $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{COOH}$
 14; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$
 15; $\text{R}_1 = \text{COOEt}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{COOMe}$

- 16; $\text{R} = \text{Me}$
 17; $\text{R} = \text{H}$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 and 577 spectrophotometers. The pmr spectra were recorded in different laboratories using TMS as an internal standard.

Methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-*N*-methylindole-3-acetate (2): A mixture of 2-carboxy-*N*-methylindole-3-acetic acid (1; 5.0 g), dry methanol (40 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (1 ml) was refluxed (10 h) on a water-bath. Methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-*N*-methylindole-3-acetate was obtained as colourless needles (methanol), m.p. 90° (Found: C, 64.2; H, 5.6. $C_{14}H_{11}NO_4$ requires: C, 64.3; H, 5.7%); ν_{max} 1730 and 1710 cm^{-1} .

3-Acetyl-*N*-methylindole-2-carboxylic acid (3): The pyran (10; 0.4 g) was refluxed (2 h) with sodium hydroxide solution (5 ml; 10%). On usual work up 3-acetyl-*N*-methylindole-2-carboxylic acid (3) was obtained as a yellow crystalline solid (0.25 g) from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 155° (Found: C, 67.4; H, 5.5. $C_{15}H_{13}NO_3$ requires: C, 67.5; H, 5.6%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid in orange crystals, m.p. 242°d (Found: N, 16.9. $C_{19}H_{17}N_2O_6$ requires: N, 17.0%).

1,3-Dioxo-9-methyl-1*H*,3*H*,4*H*,9*H*-indolo-[2,3-*c*]pyran (6): A mixture of 2-carboxy-*N*-methylindole-3-acetic acid (1 g), dry benzene (15 ml) and acetyl chloride (2 ml) was refluxed (2 h) on a water-bath, concentrated, cooled and the anhydride (6) was collected, washed (benzene) and crystallised (benzene), m.p. 199° (lit.* m.p. 199°).

Oxalyl derivative (5): A mixture of the ester (2; 0.5 g), ethyl oxalate (0.3 g) and sodium methoxide (from 0.3 g sodium) in benzene (15 ml) was kept in a refrigerator (24 h). On usual work up the oxalyl derivative (5) was obtained as yellow needles from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 175° (Found: C, 59.6; H, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{19}NO_7$ requires: C, 59.8; H, 5.3%).

This oxalyl derivative (5; 0.5 g) when refluxed (130°) in an oil-bath for 3 h with a mixture of acetic acid (4 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 ml) gave 1-oxo-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-methoxycarbonyl-9-methyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo-[2,3-*c*]pyran (15) as reddish crystals from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 184° (Found: C, 61.7; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{15}NO_6$ requires: C, 62.0; H, 4.5%).

Acylation of 2-carboxy-*N*-methylindole-3-acetic acid: At steam-bath temperature: A mixture of the acetic acid (1; 1.0 g), acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) was heated (2 h) on a boiling water-bath. The mixture on working up with concentrated HCl (4 ml) gave a sticky mass which was extracted with ethyl acetate-benzene from which extraction with sodium hydrogen carbonate gave 1-oxo-3,9-dimethyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo-[2,3-*c*]pyran-4-carboxylic acid (8) as colourless flakes (0.2 g) from acetic acid, m.p. 297°d (Found: C, 65.3; H, 4.1.

$C_{14}H_{11}NO_4$ requires: C, 65.3; H, 4.3%). The organic layer on concentration gave 7 as fine yellow needles (0.2 g), m.p. 292° (Found: C, 76.4; H, 4.7. $C_{26}H_{20}N_2O_8$ requires: C, 76.5; H, 4.9%). The mother liquor was evaporated and the organic matter extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) which afforded 9 crystallising from petroleum ether in yellow needles, m.p. 123° (Found: C, 70.4; H, 5.0. $C_{15}H_{13}NO_3$ requires: C, 70.5; H, 5.1%). At room temperature: The acetic acid (1; 1.0 g) was added slowly to a mixture of acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) with stirring. After 1 h more acetic anhydride (1 ml) was added. The acid went into solution and after 2-3 h, 1-oxo-3-acetoxy-4-acetyl-9-methyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]pyran (10; 0.7 g) separated crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 157° (Found: C, 64.3; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{13}NO_3$ requires: C, 64.2; H, 4.3%).

1-Oxo-3,9-dimethyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]pyran (11): 1-Oxo-3,9-dimethyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]pyran-4-carboxylic acid (8; 0.1 g) and copper bronze powder (0.03 g) were heated in a metal-bath at 310° for 30 min. The residue was extracted with benzene, washed with saturated bicarbonate solution and then with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). The pyran (11) crystallised (benzene-petroleum ether) in needles (0.02 g), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{11}NO_2$ requires: C, 73.2; H, 5.2%).

1-Oxo-4-methoxycarbonyl-9-methyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo-[2,3-*c*]pyran (12): A mixture of methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-*N*-methylindole-3-acetate (1.3 g), freshly distilled methyl formate (6 ml) and dry sodium methoxide (from 0.3 g Na) in dry ether (15 ml) was kept in a refrigerator for 30 h. The mixture was then refluxed (3 h) with more methyl formate (4 ml), water added, and ether layer separated. Methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-*N*-methylindole-3- α -formyl acetate (4) was obtained as fine colourless crystals (0.5 g), m.p. 99° (Found: C, 61.9; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{18}NO_5$ requires: C, 62.2; H, 5.2%); soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution; gave an intense violet colouration with ferric chloride solution. This formyl derivative (0.2 g) on heating (15 min) on a boiling water-bath with a mixture of acetic acid (2 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml) afforded 1-oxo-4-methoxycarbonyl-9-methyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo-[2,3-*c*]pyran (12) as yellow crystals (0.1 g) from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 164° (Found: C, 65.0; H, 4.1. $C_{14}H_{11}NO_4$ requires: C, 65.3; H, 4.3%).

1-Oxo-9-methyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]pyran-4-carboxylic acid (13): A mixture of compound 9, acetic acid (4 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath at 130° for 2 h, then extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. Acidification afforded 1-oxo-9-methyl-1*H*,9*H*-indolo-[2,3-*c*]pyran-4-carboxylic acid which was crystallised from methanol as fine colourless flakes (0.15 g), m.p. 249°d (Found: C, 64.0; H, 3.6. $C_{18}H_{19}NO_4$ requires: C, 64.2; H, 3.7%).

1-Oxo-9-methyl-1H,9H-indolo[2,3-c]pyran (14): The acid (**13**; 0.1 g) was mixed with copper-bronze powder (0.03 g) and heated (30 min) in a metal-bath at 270–80°, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with saturated NaHCO₃ solution, water and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of solvent afforded 1-oxo-9-methyl-1H,9H-indolo[2,3-c]pyran (**14**) as yellow needles on crystallisation from petroleum ether, (0.02 g), m.p. 132° (Found: C, 72.2; H, 4.5. C₁₂H₉NO₂ requires: C, 72.3; H, 4.5%).

1-Oxo-3,9-dimethyl-1H,2H,9H-indolo-[2,3-c]pyridine (16): A solution of compound **8** (0.1 g) in alcohol was saturated with dry ammonia and heated in a sealed tube at 150–60° for 6 h. Usual work up gave 1-oxo-3,9-dimethyl-1H, 2H,9H-indolo[2,3-c]-pyridine (0.02 g) as yellow needles (alcohol), m.p. 228°d (Found: C, 73.4; H, 5.8; N, 12.9. C₁₂H₁₂N₂O requires: C, 73.6; H, 5.7; N, 13.2%).

1-Oxo-9-methyl-1H,2H,9H-indolo[2,3-c]-pyridine (17): A mixture of the pyran (**14**; 0.02 g), ethanol (5 ml) and liquor ammonia (6 ml) was refluxed (6 h) on a water-bath. Additional amount of liquor ammonia (1 ml) was added during the course of reaction, mixture left overnight and then refluxed

again with more liquor ammonia (1 ml) for 2 h. Usual work up afforded **17** (0.01 g) as grey crystals (aqueous alcohol), m.p. 242° (lit.⁸ m.p. 242°) (Found: C, 72.6; H, 5.0; N, 13.9. C₁₂H₁₀N₂O requires: C, 72.7; H, 5.1; N, 14.1%). The compound exhibited fluorescence in acidic and alkaline solution.

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